

Low Phenylalanine Rich Dietary Regime As A Plausible Intervention Toward COVID-19 Management

Tags: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; Low Phenylalanine Diet; Phenylketonuria

Presently, SARS-CoV-2 virus (cause of COVID-19) as an unprecedented challenge before mankind is direly pressing for much effective antidote. Here, I wish to forward a theoretical contemplation regarding dietary intervention as one plausible way to manage SARS-CoV-2 multiplication in vulnerable human cells. SARS-CoV-2 has several proteins that help to complete its life cycle in human. Protein sequences of six SARS-CoV-2 proteins namely Spike (S), Envelope (E), Membrane (M), Nucleoprotein (N), nsp12 & ORF10, analyzed in this study indicated phenylalanine composition in the range of 3.1%-10.5%, suggesting phenylalanine as an important constituent in them. It can be predicted that if phenylalanine abundance in the host cell's amino acid pool is very low or is completely nil, translation of at least these six SARS-CoV-2 proteins may be affected negatively. This in turn might halt efficient viral multiplication within the infected host cells. The idea is following a temporary dietary regime comprising low phenylalanine rich foods (as advised to patients with phenylketonuria) may possibly have inhibitory affect on SARS-CoV-2 multiplication considering cellular amino acid pool would have significantly low phenylalanine abundance. Further, a recent opinion letter citing severity of COVID-19 in phenylketonuria patients could be lower due to some yet unknown reasons calls for a critical investigation.

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Experiment:

Amino Acid Composition Analyses of Six SARS-CoV-2 Proteins using <https://web.expasy.org/protparam/> tool:

[1] S-Protein

>sp|PODTC2|SPIKE_SARS2 Spike glycoprotein OS=Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 OX=2697049 GN=S PE=1 SV=1 [Length: 1, 273 aa]

MFVFLVLLPLVSSQCVNLTTRTQLPPAYTNSFTRGVYYPDKVFRSSVLHSTQDLFLPFFS
NVTWFHAIHVSGTNGTKRFDNPVLPFNDGVYFASTEKSNIRGWIFGTTLDLSDKTSLLIV
NNATNVVIVKVEFQFCNDPFLGVYYHKNNKSWMESEFRVYSSANNCTFEYVSQPFLMDLE
GKQGNFKNLREFVFNIDGYFKIYSKHTPINLVRDLPQGFSALEPLVDLPIGINITRFQT
LLALHRSYLTPGDSSSGWTAGAAAYVGYLQPRTFLLKYNENGTITDAVDCALDPLSETK

CTLKSFTVEKGIYQTSNFRVQPTESIVRFPNITNLCPFGEVFNATRFASVYAWNRKRISN
CVADYSVLYNSASFSTFKCYGVSPTKLNDLCFTNVYADSFVIRGDEVRQIAPGQTGKIAD
YNYKLPDDFTGCVIAWNSNNLDSKVGGNYNLYRLFRKSNLKPFERDISTEIQAGSTPC
NGVEGFNCYFPLQSYGFQPTNGVGYQPYRVVLSFELLHAPATVCGPKKSTNLVKNKCVN
FNFNGLTGTGVLTESNKKFLPFQQFGRDIADTTDAVRDPQTLEILDITPCSFGGVSVITP
GTNTSNQVAVLYQDVNCTEVPVAIHADQLTPTWRVYSTGSNVFQTRAGCLIGAEHVNSY
ECDIPIGAGICASYQTQTNSPRRARSVASQSIAYTMSLGAENSVAYSNNNSIAIPTNFTI
SVTTEILPVSMTKTSVDCTMYICGDSTECNLLLQYGSFCTQLNRALTGIAVEQDKNTQE
VFAQVKQIYKTPPIKDFGGFNFSQILPDPSPKSRSFIEDLLFNKVTLADAGFIKQYGDC
LGDIAARDLICAQKFNGLTVLPLLTDEMIAQYTSALLAGTITSGWTFGAGAALQIPFAM
QMAYRFNGIGVTQNVLYENQKLIANQFNSAIGKIQDLSSTASALGKLQDVVNQNAQALN
TLVKQLSSNFGAISSVLNDILSRDKVEAEVQIDRLITGRLQSLQTYVTQQLIRAAEIRA
SANLAATKMSECVLGQSKRVDFCGKGYHLMSFPQSAPHGVVFLHVTVPAQEKNFTTAPA
ICHDGKAHFPREGVFSNGTHWFVTQRNFYEPQIITTDNTFVSGNCDVVIGIVNNTVYDP
LQPELDSFKEELDKYFKNHTSPDVDLGDISGINASVVNIQKEIDRLNEVAKNLNESLIDL
QELGKYEQYIKWPWYIWLGFIAGLIAIVMVTIMLCCMTSCCCLKGCCSCGSCCKFDEDD
SEPVLKGVKLHYT

COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS

(extremes relative to: swp23s.q)

A : 79(6.2%); C : 40(3.1%); D : 62(4.9%); E : 48(3.8%); **F : 77(6.0%)**
G : 82(6.4%); H : 17(1.3%); I : 76(6.0%); K : 61(4.8%); L : 108(8.5%)
M : 14(1.1%); N : 88(6.9%); P : 58(4.6%); Q : 62(4.9%); R : 42(3.3%)
S : 99(7.8%); T : 97(7.6%); V : 97(7.6%); W : 12(0.9%); Y : 54(4.2%)

[2] E- Protein

>sp|PODTC4|VEMP_SARS2 Envelope small membrane protein OS=Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 OX=2697049 GN=E PE=1 SV=1 (75 aa)

MYSFVSEETGLIVNSVLLFLAFVVFLVTLAILTALRLCAYCCNIVNVSLVKPSFYVYS
RVKNLNSSRVPDLLV

COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS

(extremes relative to: swp23s.q)

A : 4(5.3%); C : 3(4.0%); D : 1(1.3%); E : 2(2.7%); **F : 5(6.7%)**
G : 1(1.3%); H : 0(0.0%); I : 3(4.0%); K : 2(2.7%); L : 14(18.7%)
M : 1(1.3%); N : 5(6.7%); P : 2(2.7%); Q : 0(0.0%); R : 3(4.0%)
S : 8(10.7%); T : 4(5.3%); V : 13(17.3%); W : 0(0.0%); Y : 4(5.3%)

[3] M-Protein

>sp|PODTC5|VME1_SARS2 Membrane protein OS=Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 OX=2697049 GN=M PE=1 SV=1 [222 aa]

MADSNGTITVEELKKLLEQWNLVIGFLFLTWICLLQFAYANRRNFLYIIKLIFLWLLWPV
TLACFVLAAYRINWITGGIAIAMAQLVGLMWLSYFIASFRLFARTRSMWSFNPETNILL
NVPLHGTILTRPILLESELVIGAVILRGHLRIAGHHLGRCDIKDLPKEITVATSRTLSSYYK

LGASQRVAGDSGFAAYSRYRIGNYKLNTDHSSSSDNIALLVQ

COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS

(extremes relative to: swp23s.q)

A : 19(8.6%); C : 4(1.8%); D : 6(2.7%); E : 7(3.2%); **F : 11(5.0%)**
G : 14(6.3%); H : 5(2.3%); I : 20(9.0%); K : 7(3.2%); L+ : 35(15.8%)
M : 4(1.8%); N : 11(5.0%); P : 5(2.3%); Q : 4(1.8%); R : 14(6.3%)
S : 15(6.8%); T : 13(5.9%); V : 12(5.4%); W+ : 7(3.2%); Y : 9(4.1%)

[4] N-Protein

>sp|PODTC9|NCAP_SARS2 Nucleoprotein OS=Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 OX=2697049 GN=N PE=1 SV=1 [419 aa]

MSDNGPQNQRNAPRITFGGSPDSTGSNQNNGERSGARSKQRRPQGLPNNTASWFTALTQHG
KEDLKFPRGQGVPIINTNSSPDDQIGYYRRATRIRGGDGKMKDLSPRWYFYLLGTGPEAG
LPYGANKDGIIWVATEGALNTPKDHIGTRNPANNAIIVLQLPQGTTLPKGFYAEGSRGGS
QASSRSSRSRNSSRNSTPGSSRGTSPARMAGNGGDAALALLLDRLNQLESKMSGKGQQ
QQGQTVTKKSAEASKPRQKRTATKAYNVTQAFGRRGPEQTQGNFGDQELIRQGTDYKH
WPQIAQFAPSASAFFGMSRIGMEVTPSGTWLTYTGAIKLDDKDPNFKDQVILLNKHIDAY
KTFPPTPKKDKKKKADETQALPQRQKKQQTVTLLPAADLDDFSKQLQQSMSSADSTQA

COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS

(extremes relative to: swp23s.q)

A : 37(8.8%); C : 0(0.0%); D : 24(5.7%); E : 12(2.9%); **F : 13(3.1%)**
G : 43(10.3%); H : 4(1.0%); I : 14(3.3%); K : 31(7.4%); L : 27(6.4%)
M : 7(1.7%); N : 22(5.3%); P : 28(6.7%); Q+ : 35(8.4%); R : 29(6.9%)
S : 37(8.8%); T : 32(7.6%); V-- : 8(1.9%); W : 5(1.2%); Y : 11(2.6%)

[5] nsp12-Protein

>tr|A0A0G2RC73|A0A0G2RC73_CVHOC ORF1ab polyprotein (Fragment) OS=Human coronavirus OC43 OX=31631 GN=nsp12 PE=3 SV=1 [928 aa]

SKDTNFLNRVGRASVDARLVPCASGLSTDVQLRAFDIYNASVAGIGLHLKVNCCRFQRVD
ENGDKLDQFFVVKRTDLTIYNREMKCYERVKCKFVAEHDFFTFDVEGSRVPHIVRKDLT
KYTMLDLCYALRHFDNRDCMLLCDILSIYAGCEQSYFTKKDWYDFVENPDIINVYKLG
IFNRALVSATEFADKLVEVGLVGLVTLNQLDLNGKWDYDFGDYVIAAPGCGVAIADSYSY
IMPMLTMCHALDCELYVNNAYRFLDLVQYDFDYKLELFNKYFKHWSMPYHPNTVDCQDD
RCIIHCANFNILFSMVLPNTCFGLVLRQIFVDGVPFVVSIGYHYKELGIVMNMDVDTHRY
RLSLKDLLLYAADPALHVASASALYDLRTCCFSVAAITSGVKFQTVKPGNFNQDFYDFVL
SKGLLEKGSVDLKHFFFTQDGNAAITDYNYYKYNLPTMVDIKQLLFVLEVYKYFEIYD
GGCIPASQVIVNNYDKSAGYPFNKFGKARLYYEALSFEQDEIYAYTKRNVLPTLTQMNL
KYAISAKNRARTVAGVSILSTMTGRMFHQKCLKSIAATRGPVIVIGTTKFYGGWDDMLRR
LIKDVDNPLVMGWDYPKCDRAMPNLLRIVSSLVLARKHETCCSQSDRFYRLANCAQVLS
EIVMCGGCYVVKPGGTSSGDATTAFAVSVFNICQAVSANVCALMSCNGNKIEDLSIRALQ
KRLYSHVYRSDKVDSTFVTEYEFNLKHFMMILSDDGVVCYNSDYASKGYIANISAFQQ
VLYYQNNVFMSESKCWVEYDINNGPHEFCSQHTMLVKMDGDDVYLPYPNPSRILGAGCFV
DILLKTDSVLLIERFVSLAIDAYPLVYHENEYQKVRVYLYAYIKKLYNDLGNQILDSYS
VILSTCDGQKFTDESFYKNMYLRSVVMQ

COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS

(extremes relative to: swp23s.q)

A : 59(6.4%); C : 34(3.7%); D : 73(7.9%); E : 33(3.6%); **F : 53(5.7%)**
G : 48(5.2%); H : 19(2.0%); I : 45(4.8%); K : 54(5.8%); L : 87(9.4%)
M : 26(2.8%); N : 51(5.5%); P : 27(2.9%); Q : 28(3.0%); R : 40(4.3%)
S : 59(6.4%); T : 40(4.3%); V : 80(8.6%); W : 6(0.6%); Y++: 66(7.1%)

[6] ORF10 protein

NCBI Reference Sequence: YP_009725255.1

>YP_009725255.1 ORF10 protein [Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2]

MGYINVFAFPFTIYSLLLCRMNSRNYIAQVDVVNFNLT

COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS

(extremes relative to: swp23s.q)

A : 2(5.3%); C : 1(2.6%); D : 1(2.6%); E : 0(0.0%); **F : 4(10.5%)**
G : 1(2.6%); H : 0(0.0%); I : 3(7.9%); K : 0(0.0%); L : 4(10.5%)
M : 2(5.3%); N : 5(13.2%); P : 1(2.6%); Q : 1(2.6%); R : 2(5.3%)
S : 2(5.3%); T : 2(5.3%); V : 4(10.5%); W : 0(0.0%); Y : 3(7.9%)